

TECHNOLOGICAL CAPABILITIES OF THE BIG SOLAR FURNACE IN PARKENT: CURRENT STATUS AND ANALYSIS

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The BSF makes it possible to implement technological possibilities in the synthesis of ceramic materials with a set of desired properties. The advantages of this method using solar energy are obvious [52-56]:

- there is no contamination of the target materials;
- the possibility of simultaneous purification in the synthesis process;
- the variation of the heating rate over a wide range;
- the ability to control the cooling rate, which allows to obtain materials with a given structure;
- the possibility of obtaining complex composites;
- materials have a structure that cannot be obtained by conventional methods, and it makes it possible to realize the characteristics in extremely and difficult operating conditions;
- the possibility of combination with any other method in the technological chain of synthesis of target materials, etc.;
- synthesis occurs in the liquid phase, which determines the completeness of the synthesis and the stoichiometry of the target material, and the process is accelerated hundreds and thousands of times;
- heating of initial components is carried out, practically without inertia;
- a substance is affected by a powerful photon flux with a very wide range of energies, resulting in the formation of all possible metastable states for a given substance or compound. This leads to distortions of the crystal lattice. As a result, the heat resistance and strength of the target material increases sharply, since there is no secondary recrystallization and crack growth above the critical size value;
- all acceptable photochemical processes in this energy range occur during the synthesis

A method for obtaining ceramic particles by processing man-made waste from the mining and metallurgical industry has been developed. The regulation of the properties of ceramics is possible by changing its composition and changing technological parameters at various stages of sintes process. A special polymer film containing 0.5-2.5% of ultrafine pulsed ceramic powder has been developed. Comparative tests were carried out on the use of this film for drying processes, greenhouses, temperature stabilization. Exactly the same film without ceramic content was used as a control one. The original film itself is capable of converting ultraviolet (UV) radiation into the visible light. In films intended for greenhouses, the short-wavelength part of the spectrum is converted to 620-680 nm by functional ceramics, which contributes not only to highly efficient photosynthesis, but also activates phytochrome. This allows accelerating the development of

plants, and also increases its resistance to adverse factors. A film with functional ceramics is also capable of generating infrared (IR) pulses in a given spectral range [58-60].

Currently, work is underway to modernize the BSF and replace reflective surfaces, which will achieve high energy performance, namely, increase the temperature to 3000 °C, power up to 1 MW.

Thus, there are ample opportunities to conduct researches and synthesize new materials at a high world level, to develop competitive green materials and technologies, and to provide services that are in demand on the global high-tech market.